

SUGGESTED MODEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF GLOBAL TECHNOLOGY AND OPERATIONS STRATEGY

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Abstract: *This paper describes the application of the SWOT / TOWS and Delphi method as a proposed model for decision-making process in the implementation of global technology and operational strategy on the hypothetical example of EURO EFG Bank. It is shown that this method should be considered because the proposed solutions that are based on the use of mentioned methods can contribute to a better understanding of future needs and ways of implementation and integration of global technology and operational strategies. In the system of decision-making in banking sector, when considering transfer and implementation of new technologies, time and cost benefit that offers a new model of decision-making is very important. This paper has value for Eurobank EFG Bank, and for other banking and corporation systems as well as educational institutions.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Technology as an application or an organization of knowledge for practical goals are constantly created and amended as potential opportunities for development and dissemination of new knowledge can be regarded as unlimited and the time it takes to convert scientific achievements in technology are becoming shorter and shorter. In this paper, for the most part it is represented a horizontal review of technology transfer. One of the participants in the process of transfer has already been defined according to the survey, which is the EFG Euro Bank.

Model that is presented could be sustainable part of strategic management that is led by economic imperative as a worldwide strategy based on cost leadership, differentiation and segmentation. [1]

Eurobank EFG (hereafter: EFG) is a European banking organization, offering variety of services in the banking sector, including asset management, insurance and other related services in the Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe, Great Britain and Luxembourg. In 2010 EFG total assets reached €81.9bn. EFG is a member of Eurobank EFG Group, an international banking group, operating in more than 40 countries. [2]

EFG launched its operations in Serbia in 2003 and is functioning in accordance with the national legal framework. [3]

In 2006 the National Savings Bank merged with EFG. At present EFG operates through a large network of branches throughout Serbia, offering variety of standard and innovative banking products to its clients. Furthermore, it preserves one of the leading positions in the most dynamic segments of the banking business i.e. in Small Business, Mortgage and Consumer Loans, Credit Cards, Savings and Money market operations. EFG's growth was closely followed by investments in technical and operational infrastructure (over 500 million EUR), in human capital, as well as in development of modern banking products and services designed to meet clients' needs. 2010 was marked with successes, this despite challenges in business environment and the effects of the global economic crisis as reflected in the following indicators:

- Significant rise of 23% in total assets,
- 3rd position in the market as per total assets and a market share of 7.1%,
- 3rd bank in total deposits and 4th in total equity,
- Acquired Net profit of RSD 2.6 billion,
- 24% increase in gross loan portfolio,
- Further reduction of impairment charges (22% lower than in 2009) following wise expansion policy.

2. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS IN IMPLEMENTING GLOBAL TECHNOLOGY AND OPERATIONS STRATEGY – SWOT & TOWS ANALYSIS

SWOT stands for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. It provides “raw material” as a basic listing of conditions inside and outside of company. [4]

In order to conduct SWOT, followed by TOWS analysis, specific ICT in E-banking service was elaborated from aspect of core competences of EURO EFG Bank. Core competence provides potential access to a wide variety of markets, and should make a significant contribution to the perceived customer benefits of the end product. Core competence should be difficult to be copied and implemented on side of competency. [5] Following facts are just briefly outlining the main features of the E-banking in Serbia:

- the relevant legal framework is in place, however to the most parts this issue is related to contractual relations with the clients,
- the service is underdeveloped [6], but significant inner strengths coupled with the knowledge gained by other countries advanced in this field provide an excellent platform for the service's upgrade,
- there is a growing demand for this type of service,
- its further expansion will enable local companies smoother integration in the European, as well global market.

For the EFG full implementation of E-banking would further contribute to:

- enhancement of business efficiency and productivity,
- reduction of business expenses.

In the Round 1: Opportunities and threats related to further upgrading/promotion of E-banking Service in EFG were identified. Three most significant indicators recognized in the external environment as the opportunities, thus in correlation with further upgrading of E-banking service are: growing demand for this type of services, ICT development supporting service, global, regional and local inter-connections. As the present and predicted future threats three distinct indicators were identified: fraud issue linked with E-banking, competition from other banks, impact from the present and the new wave of economic crisis.

In the Round 2: Strengths and weaknesses i.e. internal EFG environment in the context of an upgrade of the E-banking service were elaborated. The inner strengths are: technology know how, strong service network and the relevant IT support. These were then combined with internal weaknesses: security issue, operational risk, lack of data privacy. Internal weaknesses in this case are also a reflection of threat arising from external environment i.e. fraud issue.

Round 3 was dedicated to mapping/combining the indicators/cells, both related to internal and external environment

against the usage of E-banking services, referring to Strengths & Opportunities, Weaknesses & Opportunities, Strengths & Threats, and Weaknesses & Threats.

Final Round 4 led to tailoring of strategies:

- SO - Competitive advantages of EFG in further promoting E-banking services are clearly marked, while future strategies to match with external opportunities should be firmly anchored in EFG strengths (in ICT sector).
- WO - Again, skilled employees in EFG IT department, combined with existing know how are providing strong arguments in tailoring of future strategies for the advance investments in ICT. Present weaknesses are outlining the need for additional investing.
- ST - This section maps the “mobilization” strategies, whereas inner strengths and outer threats are confronted.
- WT - This section provides an overview of “damage control” strategies.

Table 1, SWOT/TOWS Analyses, provided by the author

Internal Factors	Strengths - technology know how - strong service network - relevant IT support	Weaknesses -security issue -operational risk -data privacy
External factors		
Opportunities - growing demand for this type of services - ICT development supporting service - global and local inter connection	SO - Further promote practical usage of technology deployed in EFG to match the growing needs of the market - Follow closely relevant ICT development, continue vigorous trainings of employees - Local, regional, global expansion offering relevant services and strong IT support	WO - Further investing in control and protection of transactions and users - Follow closely relevant ICT development in order to minimize the risks in operations - Further improvement of technologies related to data protection, as well in innovations
Threats - fraud issue - competition from other banks - economic crisis	ST - Further development of technological know how to minimize frauds - Challenge competition with even higher quality of services rendered throughout EFG network - Deploy all available capacities to minimize the effects of global crisis	WT - Investing further in ICT to overcome both weaknesses and threats related to security and fraud - Reduce threat of competition by deploying early risks' assessments, also by introducing activities aimed at controlling of operational risks - Both further developing of system and services' diversification, would lead to reduction of privacy data breaches and higher security.

3. FORECASTING TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT – DELPHI METHOD

Delphi method is forecasting method “based on series of written questionnaires with feedback and re-voting.” [7] Delfi is a method of qualitative approach to forecasting and presents a good way to coalesce different opinions into a consensus which will lead company management to better understanding of experts opinion. [8]

For the purpose of this paper “design group” is the group of EFG Bank employees, while the “expert group” should be composed of experts in ICT sector, banking, management and sociology.

In this method a group of experts will be first asked about their individual judgments on a particular aspect of future technology. These judgments will be collected in a blind fashion where each expert is not aware of the judgments of other experts.

Different opinions leading to creation of consensus of all participants. [9]

3.1. Formulating Delphi Questionnaire for 15 arising questions

Following set of questions was designed around the usage of Information and Communication Technologies in the EFG’s operations:

Q 1. When will EFG introduce digital signature?

The relevant Serbian law provides a legal framework for introduction of digital signature in E-commerce. However, due to security concerns, this concept in banking is not widely used. Therefore EFG will start targeting specific segments in which these operations would be both secure and beneficial.

Q 2. When will 80% of EFG customers start using electronic banking services?

Customers and EFG have recognized benefits of E-banking services, first and foremost as it is less time consuming for both parties. Opportunity costs are related to other branch activities e.g. selling services-products. Number of banking procedures will be resumed in one i.e. E-banking.

Q 3. When EFG’s traditional communications with customers through i.e. branch offices will be innovated with Internet and Computer based communication channels?

The more advanced technology i.e. communication via mobile technology, internet technology, would be favorable both for customers and for the Bank. For the customers it would mean, acquiring information in a more efficient way, faster, thus less time consuming. For the EFG this would lead to additional cost cutting and even more efficient providing of services, yet more effective performing of operations.

Q 4: When will EFG in Serbia introduce SMS message system to upgrade communication flows with the clients about all questions / information in possession, existing and the new products / services of the bank?

Currently, some information are shared with the customers, but these information are limited to the basics. Therefore it would be important for EFG to expand portfolio information provided to the customers.

Q 5: When will research and development efforts in ICT sector in Serbia contribute to the 3% GDP growth in Serbia?

ICT sector is poorly developed in Serbia. There is a general link between development and the new technologies, specifically ICT. Low GDP implicates poor economic performance, while in order to perform better it would be essential to invest in R&D in this specific sector.

Q 6: When will EFG network in Serbia be covered at 100% with APS machines?

At present APS (Automated Payment System) machines are deployed at 40% capacity. Advantages of its full usage would be reflected in faster payment services, money transfer, maintaining loans’ services, thus contributing to the branches’ productivity.

Q 7: When will EFG innovate its Flexcube operating system from 7.00 to 11.00?

Present Flexcube operating system 7.00 satisfy the needs of both customers and the EFG. However with the enlargement of the customers base and envisaged merge with another bank (in line with the emerging global trend on banks merging), the introduction of the new core system version offering higher performances will be needed. Higher speed, diverse data base, flexibility are the essential values of the advanced system, providing full compliance with the bank’s need, yet making EFG more competitive.

Q 8: When will EFG deploy system for low interest loan for the students of Faculty of organiyational sciences as their potential future employees?

Currently EFG doesn’t offer banking packages to support professional development of students attending economics and management programs.

Q 9: When the banks which use the same core systems will be merged into one?

On Serbian market small number of banks are using specific core system. There is a trend of introducing Flexcube operating system, in order to contribute to the future banks merging while the underlining reasons for that merging are to be found in the need to relax effects of the financial crisis and eventual new waves of crisis.

Q 10: When will EFG introduce program for calculating employees productivity and efficiency across different departments?

Program for calculating employees' productivity and efficiency across different departments still hasn't been introduced, only excel programs are being used.

Q 11: When will Pay Pal service be available in EFG?

There is a great interest for enabling use of Pay Pal system in Serbia, while legal preconditions are already secured. Smooth functioning of this system would be beneficial both for the customer and for the EFG.

Q 12: When will internal software for corporate social responsibility towards local community be introduced?

At present information on activities referring to corporate social responsibility towards local communities are stored in branches and no unique data base containing all relevant information/activities exists.

Q 13 : When can we expect implementation of digital signature in 80% of banks in Serbia?

This would be a variation of Q 1; here it refers to the Serbian banking sector as a whole.

Q 14: When will EFG install electronic instead of manual archive?

Installation and the usage of electronic data base will be contingent upon adoption of relevant laws which would regulate storage of data.

Q 15: When will within E-banking service for transferring money abroad and vice versa be introduced?

At present this type of service is not rendered to the customers.

3.2. Calculating and reviewing results for Q1 and Q2

Question no. 1: When can we expect implementation of digital signature in our organization?

Figure 1, Delphi table, provided by the author

Figure 2, Delphi table, provided by the author

Question no. 2: When can we expect implementation of digital signature in 80% of banks in Serbia?

Figure 3, Delphi table, provided by the author

Figure 4, Delphi table, provided by the author

- Based on answers, implementation of digital signature in our organization can be expected in May 2014. (2011+3.5714)
- Based on answers, implementation of digital signature in 80% of banks in Serbia can be expected in July 2014, also. (2011+3.7143)
 - Is the level of agreement higher for the first or for the second question?
 - Level of agreement is higher for the second question.
 - Based on answers, when can we expect the implementation of new technology in the organization with probability of 90%?
 - Based on answers, implementation of digital signature in our organization with probability of 90% can be expected at the end of 2017 and the beginning of 2018.
 - Based on answers, implementation of digital signature in 80% of banks in Serbia with probability of 90% can be expected in the first quarter of 2016.

Based on this model all other questions could be configured through Delphi software in order to retrieve results.

4 CONCLUSION

SWOT and TOWS conducted for the purpose of this paper proved our starting premise related to the usage of Information and Communication Technology in contemporary business settings. Usage of ICT, specifically in the banking sector deserves a role of driving force in further growth. Constant development of ICT and its proper management is two fold: on one hand it is a powerful ground for innovation, enabling expansion of business portfolio, challenging competition. On the other its development is needed in order to respond properly to the external threats and inner weaknesses, when linked to the abuse of technologies.

Delphi Questionnaire was tailored to explore variety of interrelated issues.

Based on the above, recommendations for the managers are:

- Further develop the system in order to confront and minimize threats approaching from external environment, as well as internal weaknesses;
- Further development of new technologies is needed in order to correspond to the needs of fast growing markets and customers;
- Again for the sake of competitiveness greater diversification of systems and products is essential,
- Investing in development of new and in upgrading of existing technologies will contribute to efficiency and effectiveness in banking services performing,
- The customers will recognize quality of services, thus speed in their rendering, including less time consuming procedures in bank's branches,
- Innovative and profitable E-banking services lead to reduction of operational costs, minimization of operational risks and to overall increase of the bank profitability,
- Introduce new technologies (e.g. APS machines) in profitable branches in order to increase productivity and reduce operational costs,

- Further develop E-banking in order to reduce operational costs in performing transactions, to enlarge market potential and to respond more proper to the customers needs,
- Upgrade the core system in order to gain competitive advantage, thus being prepared for the future mergers,
- Continuously invest in employees' trainings, as well as in customers' education on the usage of services offered by the EFG (E-banking, APS).

As a result of the paper there are clear recommendations based on the results of the analyzes that are done. It is necessary to consider and include this kind of methodology in large corporations in the formation of the system of decision-making in process of the implementation of global technologies to maximize the efficiency of decision-making. Process of each implementation of global technology is time-consuming and therefore all delays should be prevented in the decision making process.

5 REFERENCES

[1] **F. Luthans, J.P.Doh:** *International management*, 7th ed., McGraw-Hill, London, ISBN 978-0-07-811257-7

[2] **EFG Group:** <<http://www.efggroup.com/>>accessed on 14th of June 2013

[3] **Euro Bank Srbija:** <<http://www.eurobankefg.rs/pocetna.1.html>>accessed on 10th of June 2013

[4] **G. G.Dess et al :** *Strategic management*, 5th ed., McGraw-Hill, 2010, ISBN 978-0-07-353041-3

[5] **R. Burgelman et all:** *Strategic management of technology and innovation* – 4th ed., McGrawHill, 2004, USA, ISBN 007-123230-3

[6] **B. Travica et all :** *E-Commerce in Serbia: Where Roads Cross Electrons Will Flow.* (2007) Journal of Global Information Technology Management, 10(2), retrieved from http://umanitoba.academia.edu/BobTravica/Papers/384184/E-COMMERCE_IN_SERBIA_A_CASE_STUDY,

[7] **S.Marinkovic et all:** *Quality in Services: Higher Education, Health Care, Local Government, Tourism, Banking.* 2008, Proceedings of the 11th Toulon-Verona International Conference. Florence, Italy, retrieved from www.fupress.com/Archivio/pdf%5C2833.pdf

[8] **J. A. Lawrance et all:** *Applied management science*, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 2002, USA, ISBN 0-471-39190-5

[9] **O.S.Yu et all:** *Technology Portfolio Planning and management*, Springer, USA, 2006, ISBN10: 0-387-35446-8

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